

Points covered in the Final Project

1. The final project will be carried out in pairs. Each pair should choose a Java project or a React TypeScript project below.
2. For each project, contributions should be made to open-source code projects aimed at improving the code. (Acceptance of contributions will not be mandatory, but they must be submitted)
3. Initially, there will be a warm-up stage where students should get to know the projects better, solve minor issues, and open issues that can be resolved by improving code quality.
4. In each project, at least 20 code smells of 4 different types of code smells should be identified.
5. For Java projects, detection should be done using the PMD tool, and for React TypeScript projects, detection is done using the ReactSniffer tool. (Link below)
6. Before changing the code, quality measurements should be made with the Understand tool. (See metrics below)
7. Based on the detection of code smells, refactor one type of code smell at a time. Indicate in the provided diary the difficulties encountered during refactoring and the refactoring techniques used.
8. After each refactoring of a type of code smell, measure the metrics in the Understand tool and analyze if there was a benefit to the code quality.
9. Before submitting the contribution of the refactoring, review the refactored code and indicate in the diary the changes made in relation to the review.

10. In the submission of the contribution, indicate exactly the modification and improvement in quality compared to the metrics obtained with the change.

11. Those who have their contribution accepted in the project will gain 1 extra point in the final project.

Description of React code smells:

React Code Smells: <https://github.com/fabiosferreira/React-Code-Smells>

React TypeScript Code Smells:

<https://github.com/maykongsn/react-typescript-code-smells>

TOOLS:

PMD: <https://pmd.github.io/>

ReactSniffer: <https://github.com/maykongsn/reactsniffer>

Understand Tool: <https://scitools.com/student>

Metrics board

Metrics from Understand to collect (React TypeScript)	Metrics from Understand to collect (Java)
AvgCyclomatic	PercentLackOfCohesion
CountDeclFunction	CountClassCoupled
CountLine	SumCyclomatic
CountLineComment	MaxNesting
Cyclomatic	CountClassDerived
MaxNesting	CountClassBase
SumCyclomatic	MaxInheritanceTree